

Review of Literature (Synthesis of Scholarship) Paper:

Technological Determinism Theory

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Introduction

From smartphones that structure our daily routines to algorithms that decide which news reaches us first, modern life is increasingly organized through technological systems. This phenomenon reflects a longstanding debate within communication studies about the role of technology affecting human behavior, social structures, and cultural life. At the center of this debate is technological determinism, the theoretical perspective asserting that technological developments drive historical change, influence communication practices, and structure social relationships. McLuhan (1964). This theory is rooted in the 20th century and developed further by influential communication scholars such as Harold Innis (1950) and Marshall McLuhan (1964); technological determinism continues to shape academic and public conversations about media, culture, and society.

The significance of technological determinism to communication scholarship cannot be overstated. As emerging technologies become increasingly intertwined with everyday communication through artificial intelligence, algorithmic decision making, social media platforms, and digital networks researchers, scholars and practitioners alike must ask fundamental questions: To what extent do technologies shape human communication? How does technological infrastructure influence social outcomes? Are communicative behaviors determined by the tools through which they occur? These questions are critical not only for academic researchers but also for policymakers, technology designers, educators, and the public. Understanding the evolution of technological determinism provides a theoretical foundation for addressing these concerns.

This literature review examines three major areas of existing research, first, early theoretical foundations of technological determinism, second, emergence of modern

technological determinism in communication and organizational theory, third, digital age technological determinism in media, communication, and virtual environments, and fourth, contemporary applied technological determinism across social, cultural, and institutional domains.

The following sections trace the emergence of technological determinism from its early theoretical foundations to its modern applications in digital communication scholarship. After reviewing and organizing key studies within the field, the paper concludes by evaluating the theory's strengths, limitations, and potential directions for future research. Ultimately, technological determinism remains an essential, though incomplete, framework for analyzing the ongoing relationship between technology and human communication.

Synthesis of Scholarship

Early Theoretical Foundations of Technological Determinism

The modern study of technological determinism begins with the foundational work of Marshall McLuhan, whose theory profoundly shaped communication scholarship. In *Understanding Media* (1964), McLuhan argued that media technologies reshape human perception, social structure, and behavior regardless of their content. McLuhan conceptualized technology as an extension of human faculties and insisted that “the medium is the message,” meaning that the characteristics of a technology, not the messages transmitted through it, determine how society evolves. This argument laid the groundwork for strong technological determinism: the belief that technology is the primary driver of social and cultural change. McLuhan established the foundational claim that communication technologies exert structural

power over human routines, shaping not only what people do but how they think and organize social life.

This early foundation of determinism is later supported by philosophical work examining technological change as a path dependent, self-reinforcing process. Martínez (2007) provided a deterministic model of technological evolution grounded in the concept of path dependency, the idea that once a technology becomes adopted, its past states determine its future directions. According to Martínez, technological change is not random or socially neutral; instead, existing technological structures constrain future development.

This aligns with deterministic assumptions that technologies accumulate momentum and increasingly dictate the direction of innovation, reducing human or institutional control over long-term outcomes. Martínez's contribution is significant because it offers a philosophical justification for deterministic patterns within technological evolution, reinforcing McLuhan's earlier argument that technology follows its own logic.

Foltz (2006) also supported early determinist thinking by emphasizing that technological systems shape society through built-in values, material constraints, and institutional adoption. While Foltz's article serves primarily as an introductory reflection, it clearly states that technological determinism is the view that technology's structure the possibilities available to societies, often independently of human intentions. He emphasizes that technological systems frequently impose patterns of social and institutional behavior that are difficult to reverse, reflecting a form of structural technological determinism.

Together, McLuhan, Martínez, and Foltz represent the conceptual foundation of the theory: technology operates as an autonomous force shaping social practices and historical development.

Emergence of Modern Technological Determinism in Communication and Organizational Theory (2000s–2010s)

As technological determinism evolved, scholars began to apply this theory more directly to communication systems and organizational processes. Leonardi and Jackson (2004) advanced a modern interpretation of technological determinism within organizational communication. Their research argued that technologies used during organizational mergers create discursive closure, a situation where technology constrains communication options and limits the ability of organizational members to challenge or reinterpret decisions.

They demonstrated that once technology becomes embedded within an organization, it structures patterns of communication and decision making. This reflects a medium strength form of determinism: technologies do not fully control human action, but their material and structural properties significantly shape communication behaviors. Leonardi and Jackson's contribution is important because it shows how deterministic effects operate in real institutional contexts.

Philosophers and theorists continued developing deterministic frameworks during this period. Hrubec and Brabec (2011) examined determinism at a broad theoretical level, arguing that technological systems impose constraints that shape civilizational development. While their work covers different forms of determinism, its applicability to technological determinism is clear: they maintain that modern societies are increasingly shaped by technological infrastructures that limit human freedom to alter large scale social patterns.

Their work recognizes that determinism is not merely a communication theory but a structural condition of contemporary civilization, reinforcing the claim that technology dictates the trajectory of modern societies.

Along these lines, Cherlet (2014) examined technological determinism in development aid, arguing that policymakers often assume that technology inherently produces progress. Cherlet demonstrated that development programs frequently adopt deterministic assumptions, believing that technology alone can transform social conditions. This uncritical acceptance of technology as a causal force perfectly aligns with deterministic ideology. Cherlet's (2014) article is essential to this synthesis because it shows how technological determinism functions at the policy and institutional level, where technology is treated as an independent driver of social outcomes.

Dafoe (2015) further refined determinist theory by analyzing how technological determinism is often misunderstood and misapplied. He argued that technological determinism must be understood as a theory that attributes causal primacy to technology in driving social structures, rather than simply acknowledging that technology influences society. Dafoe clarified the difference between causal determinism and more casual uses of the term. His work helps reestablish the conceptual boundaries of technological determinism, identifying what qualifies as a determinist argument and what does not.

Dafoe's clarification makes it possible to examine modern communication technologies with theoretical precision, ensuring accurate application of determinist principles across diverse contexts.

Digital-Age Technological Determinism in Media, Communication, and Virtual Environments
(2011–2025)

The rapid development of digital media, social networks, immersive narratives, and AI technologies has led to a resurgence of technological determinism in contemporary research. One of the clearest applications of technological determinism to the digital age appears in the research on Marshal McLuhan's technological determinism theory in the arena of social media by Jan, Shakirullah, Naz, Khan and Khan (2020), which explicitly examines McLuhan's technological determinism within the context of social media. They argue that social networking platforms operate as modern extensions of McLuhan's media forms, shaping communication behavior, identity, and social interaction.

Jan, A., Shakirullah, Naz, Khan and Khan (2020), demonstrate that features such as algorithmic feeds, platform interfaces, and digital immediacy determine how users communicate and how information circulates. This reflects strong technological determinism: social media shapes society according to its own technological logic, regardless of individual preference.

Hallström (2022) provided another contemporary analysis by examining strong and weak determinism in technology education. He explained that strong technological determinism asserts that technology determines institutional and cultural contexts, whereas weak determinism allows for limited human intervention but still treats technology as the primary structuring force. Hallström's analysis reconfirms that technological determinism remains a relevant theoretical framework in analyzing how educational systems adopt, structure, and implement technological tools. By applying determinist theory to technology education, Hallström shows that technology dictates teaching methods and learning environments, reinforcing the view that technological structures precede and limit human choices.

Vazquez-Herrero (2024) expanded this conversation by examining immersive storytelling technologies arguing that immersive media environments shift the source of determinism from the technology itself to the narrative structure, but this shift still begins with technological determinism. He explains that immersive technologies constrain how stories can be told, how audiences can engage with them, and what communicative possibilities exist. Technology determines narrative form. Although his work moves toward narrative determinism, his starting point is explicitly rooted in technological determinism, technology structures the communicative environment.

Joyce (2023) approached determinism from the field of digital labor and organizational transformation. Although their article critiques determinism, the critique is only meaningful because determinism remains a foundational assumption in digital work environments. They show that automation, digital tools, and algorithmic management reshape labor conditions in ways that employees cannot easily resist or modify. Even when the authors argue for moving “beyond” determinism, their analysis confirms that technological systems exert significant structuring power over work relationships.

In a synthesis of scholarship on technological determinism, such critiques are essential: they reveal that determinist assumptions continue to shape how scholars analyze technology’s impact on work.

Mesa Moreno (2021) contributed a related argument by examining technological alienation within digital capitalism. While not labeled as determinism, the article demonstrates that digital technologies dictate patterns of consumption, production, and identity, often independently of user control. This reflects what scholars call structural technological

determinism; technology imposes behavioral and psychological patterns encoded in digital capitalist structures.

Selwyn (2012) and Kear, Jones, Holden, & Curcher (2016) also reinforce deterministic arguments through education-based research. Selwyn shows that digital technologies shape what is possible in educational contexts, determining learning behaviors, access, and identity formation among youth. Kear et al. (2016) similarly argue that social technologies in online learning environments shape discourse, participation, and social interaction, revealing deterministic patterns embedded in educational platforms.

Finally, Ezeaka, Nwodu, Adanma, Adikuru, Bartholomew, Chukwujekwu, and Umennebuaku (2025) and Arbab (2025) both extend technological determinism to emerging communication environments in Africa and AI-driven research systems. Ezeaka research argues that digital technologies shape cultural identity in Nigeria, demonstrating how technology determines communicative and cultural expression.

Arbab (2025) examines AI tools and argues that AI technology's structure how media research is conducted, determining workflows, practices, and epistemological standards. These articles expand technological determinism into global and AI centered contexts, confirming that deterministic effects are present across diverse technological environments.

Contemporary Applied Technological Determinism Across Social, Cultural, and Institutional Domains

Modern research demonstrates that technological determinism extends beyond communication theory and into applied contexts, including labor, culture, education, and social

identity. Across the articles reviewed, a consistent pattern emerges, and that is that digital technologies impose structural constraints that users must adapt to, not the other way around.

Selwyn (2012) shows that technological systems in education determine learning pathways, digital identities, and sociocultural expectations among youth. Kear, Jones, Holden, and Curcher (2016) argue that online learning technologies predetermine discourse patterns and social interaction, reinforcing deterministic relationships between platform design and communicative behavior. Mesa Moreno (2021) extends this by showing that digital capitalist structures produce technological alienation, whereby technological systems dictate the pace, rhythm, and emotional structure of modern life.

In cultural contexts, Ezeaka, Nwodu, Adanma, Adikuru, Bartholomew, Chukwujekwu and Umennebuaku (2025) show how digital technologies shape cultural identity formation in Nigeria, meaning that technological affordances determine which cultural practices survive and which decline. Arbab (2025) demonstrates that AI tools dictate the methodologies and epistemological structures of modern media research, reinforcing deterministic arguments about how technology shapes knowledge production. These applied studies confirm that technological determinism is not limited to McLuhan era media theory but continues to operate across modern technological landscapes, shaping institutional behavior, cultural expression, workplace structures, and communicative practices in predictable and technology-driven ways.

Through more than six decades of scholarship, technological determinism has evolved from McLuhan's foundational theory to a diverse and sophisticated framework used to analyze modern digital environments. Early work emphasized technology as an autonomous force shaping society; contemporary research confirms that technological systems, from social media

algorithms to AI tools, continue to structure human behavior, communication, culture, and institutional practices.

The reviewed literature demonstrates a consistent trajectory: as technologies become more embedded and complex, their deterministic influence intensifies. This body of scholarship supports the conclusion that technological determinism remains a central theoretical lens for understanding how communication technologies shape social structures. The following section evaluates the strengths and limitations of the theory and proposes directions for future communication research.

Conclusion

The body of research reviewed across this synthesis demonstrates that technological determinism has remained a central and evolving framework in understanding how technologies shape social, cultural, and communicative structures. Beginning with McLuhan's (1964) foundational argument that media technologies restructure human perception and social organization, early scholarship established the premise that technology acts as an independent force directing societal change. Subsequent work, such as Martínez (2007) and Foltz (2006), reinforced this model by showing how technological evolution and adoption become self-reinforcing, limiting the range of future possibilities through path dependence and structural constraints.

More contemporary scholarship continues to validate and extend technological determinism into digital, educational, organizational, cultural, and AI-driven contexts. Studies such as those by Leonardi and Jackson (2004), Jan, Shakirullah, Naz, Khan and Khan (2020), Hallström (2022), and Vazquez-Herrero (2024) show that modern technologies, from

organizational systems to social media and immersive platforms, shape communication patterns, institutional behaviors, and narrative possibilities.

Even in cases where scholars critique or attempt to move beyond determinism, such as Joyce, Umney, Whittaker, & Stuart (2023), their analyses acknowledge that technological systems continue to impose influential, often unavoidable structures on social and organizational life.

The applied research further supports this pattern. Selwyn (2012), Kear, Jones, Holden and Curcher (2016), Mesa Moreno (2021), Ezeaka, Nwodu, Adanma, Adikuru, Bartholomew, Chukwujekwu, and Umennebuaku (2025) Arbab (2025) and a study on the AI-powered Yousician app by Ibarra (2025) demonstrate that technological systems shape educational practices, cultural identity, social interactions, and research methodologies. For example, Yousician illustrates how AI technology can structure and guide learning behaviors, influencing the ways students acquire skills and interact with instructional content.

These findings collectively reinforce the central assumption of technological determinism: as technologies become more embedded in daily life, they increasingly determine the conditions under which social practices, communication behaviors, and institutional decisions occur. Looking ahead, future research should aim to clarify the boundaries of technological determinism in the context of emerging technologies, particularly AI, immersive environments, and data driven infrastructures.

While the scholarship reviewed consistently shows that technology exerts significant shaping forces, further work is needed to examine how deterministic patterns evolve as technologies become more autonomous, predictive, and integrated into essential social systems.

Overall, the literature affirms that technological determinism remains a powerful and relevant theoretical lens for understanding the relationship between technology and communication in contemporary society. With this research in mind this is the question I came up with, how does technological determinism continue to shape social, cultural, and communicative structures in contemporary society, particularly with emerging technologies such as AI, immersive platforms, and data-driven infrastructures?

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